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Correction: Plasma-induced grafting of polyacrylamide on graphene oxide nanosheets for simultaneous removal of radionuclides

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 Correction for 'Plasma-induced grafting of polyacrylamide on graphene oxide nanosheets for simultaneous removal of radionuclides' by Wencheng Song *et al.*, *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2015, **17**, 398–406.

The authors regret that the Raman in Fig. 2c and XRD in Fig. 2e of the above mentioned paper were incorrect because of confusion with other samples. Besides, the labels of the XPS N 1s spectra of PAM/GO and PAM/GO-Eu were mislabeled in Fig. 7b, and the XPS N 1s spectra of PAM/GO was reanalyzed (Table S6). Thus, the Raman of GO and GO/PAM, XRD of PAM/GO and high-resolution XPS N 1s spectra of PAM/GO and PAM/GO-Eu were corrected below. The correction has no effect to the discussion and main conclusion.

Fig. 2c Raman spectra of GO.

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Fig. 2e XRD of PAM/GO.

Fig. 7b High-resolution XPS N 1s spectra of PAM/GO and PAM/GO-Eu.

The revised curve fitting results of the XPS N 1s spectra can be found in Table S6 of the updated electronic supplementary information file alongside the original article and are also shown below:

Table S6 Curve fitting results of XPS N 1s spectra

Type		Peak	BE (eV)	FWHM (eV)	%
PAM/GO	N 1s	1	399.92	1.88	93.54
		2	401.52	1.56	6.46
PAM/GO-Eu	N 1s	1	398.70	1.96	7.16
		2	399.75	1.44	88.57
		3	401.44	1.39	4.27

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

